

ANNEX 6 Additional Information

6.1. Global Warming Potential Values

Global Warming Potential (GWP) is intended as a quantified measure of the globally averaged relative radiative forcing impacts of a particular greenhouse gas. It is defined as the cumulative radiative forcing – both direct and indirect effects—integrated over a specific period of time from the emission of a unit mass of gas relative to some reference gas (IPCC 2007). Carbon dioxide (CO₂) was chosen as this reference gas. Direct effects occur when the gas itself is a greenhouse gas. Indirect radiative forcing occurs when chemical transformations involving the original gas produce a gas or gases that are greenhouse gases, or when a gas influences other radiatively important processes such as the atmospheric lifetimes of other gases. The relationship between kilotons (kt) of a gas and million metric tons of CO₂ equivalents (MMT CO₂ Eq.) can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{MMT CO}_2 \text{ Eq.} = (\text{kt of gas}) \times (\text{GWP}) \times \left(\frac{\text{MMT}}{1,000 \text{ kt}} \right)$$

where,

MMT CO ₂ Eq.	=	Million metric tons of Carbon Dioxide Equivalents
kt	=	Kilotons (equivalent to a thousand metric tons)
GWP	=	Global Warming Potential
MMT	=	Million metric tons

GWP values allow policy makers to compare the impacts of emissions and reductions of different gases. According to the IPCC, GWP values typically have an uncertainty of ±35 percent, though some GWP values have larger uncertainty than others, especially those in which lifetimes have not yet been ascertained. In the following decision, the parties to the UNFCCC have agreed to use consistent GWP values from the *IPCC Fourth Assessment Report (AR4)*, based upon a 100 year time horizon, although other time horizon values are available (see Table A-284). While noting the specific reporting requirements of the UNFCCC this Inventory uses agreed upon GWP values, it is also noted that unweighted gas emissions and sinks in kilotons (kt) are provided in the Trends chapter of this report (Table 2-2).

*...the global warming potential values used by Parties included in Annex I to the Convention (Annex I Parties) to calculate the carbon dioxide equivalence of anthropogenic emissions by sources and removals by sinks of greenhouse gases shall be those listed in the column entitled "Global warming potential for given time horizon" in table 2.14 of the errata to the contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, based on the effects of greenhouse gases over a 100-year time horizon...*¹²¹

Greenhouse gases with relatively long atmospheric lifetimes (e.g., CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HFCs, PFCs, SF₆, and NF₃) tend to be evenly distributed throughout the atmosphere, and consequently global average concentrations can be determined. However, the short-lived gases such as water vapor, carbon monoxide, tropospheric ozone, other indirect greenhouse gases (e.g., NO_x and NMVOCs), and tropospheric aerosols (e.g., SO₂ products and black carbon) vary spatially, and consequently it is difficult to quantify their global radiative forcing impacts. GWP values are generally not attributed to these gases that are short-lived and spatially inhomogeneous in the atmosphere.

Table A-284: IPCC AR4 Global Warming Potentials (GWP) and Atmospheric Lifetimes (Years) of Gases Used in this Report

Gas	Atmospheric Lifetime	100-year GWP ^a	20-year GWP	500-year GWP
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	See footnote ^b	1	1	1
Methane (CH ₄) ^c	12.4 ^d	25	72	7.6
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	121 ^d	298	289	153
HFC-23	222	14,800	12,000	12,200
HFC-32	5.2	675	2,330	205

¹²¹ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change; < <http://unfccc.int/resource/docs/2013/cop19/eng/10a03.pdf> >; 31 January 2014; Report of the Conference of the Parties at its nineteenth session; held in Warsaw from 11 to 23 November 2013; Addendum; Part two: Action taken by the Conference of the Parties at its nineteenth session; Decision 24/CP.19; Revision of the UNFCCC reporting guidelines on annual inventories for Parties included in Annex I to the Convention; p. 2. (UNFCCC 2014)

HFC-125	28.2	3,500	6,350	1,100
HFC-134a	13.4	1,430	3,830	435
HFC-143a	47.1	4,470	5,890	1,590
HFC-152a	1.5	124	437	38
HFC-227ea	38.9	3,220	5,310	1,040
HFC-236fa	242	9,810	8,100	7,660
HFC-43-10mee	16.1	1,640	4,140	500
CF ₄	50,000 ^d	7,390	5,210	11,200
C ₂ F ₆	10,000	12,200	8,630	18,200
C ₃ F ₈	2,600	8,830	6,310	12,500
C ₄ F ₁₀	2,600	8,860	6,330	12,500
c-C ₄ F ₈	3,200	10,300	7,310	14,700
C ₅ F ₁₂	4,100	9,160	6,510	13,300
C ₆ F ₁₄	3,100	9,300	6,600	13,300
SF ₆	3,200	22,800	16,300	32,600
NF ₃	500	17,200	12,300	20,700

Source: IPCC (2007)

^a GWP values used in this report are calculated over 100 year time horizon.

^b For a given amount of carbon dioxide emitted, some fraction of the atmospheric increase in concentration is quickly absorbed by the oceans and terrestrial vegetation, some fraction of the atmospheric increase will only slowly decrease over a number of years, and a small portion of the increase will remain for many centuries or more.

^c The methane GWP includes the direct effects and those indirect effects due to the production of tropospheric ozone and stratospheric water vapor. The indirect effect due to the production of CO₂ is not included.

Table A-285 presents direct GWP values for ozone-depleting substances (ODSs). Ozone-depleting substances directly absorb infrared radiation and contribute to positive radiative forcing; however, their effect as ozone-depleters also leads to a negative radiative forcing because ozone itself is a potent greenhouse gas. There is considerable uncertainty regarding this indirect effect; therefore, a range of net GWP values is provided for ozone depleting substances. The IPCC Guidelines and the UNFCCC do not include reporting instructions for estimating emissions of ODSs because their use is being phased-out under the Montreal Protocol (see note below Table A-285). The effects of these compounds on radiative forcing are not addressed in this report.

Table A-285: 100-year Direct Global Warming Potentials for Select Ozone Depleting Substances

Gas	Direct GWP
CFC-11	4,750
CFC-12	10,900
CFC-113	6,130
HCFC-22	1,810
HCFC-123	77
HCFC-124	609
HCFC-141b	725
HCFC-142b	2,310
CH ₃ CCl ₃	146
CCl ₄	1,400
CH ₃ Br	5
Halon-1211	1,890
Halon-1301	7,140

Source: IPCC (2007)

Note: Because these compounds have been shown to deplete stratospheric ozone, they are typically referred to as ozone depleting substances (ODSs). However, they are also potent greenhouse gases. Recognizing the harmful effects of these compounds on the ozone layer, in 1987 many governments signed the *Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer* to limit the production and importation of a number of CFCs and other halogenated compounds. The United States furthered its commitment to phase-out ODSs by signing and ratifying the Copenhagen Amendments to the Montreal Protocol in 1992. Under these amendments, the United States committed to ending the production and importation of halons by 1994, and CFCs by 1996.

The IPCC published its *Fifth Assessment Report (AR5)* in 2013, providing the most current and comprehensive scientific assessment of climate change (IPCC 2013). Within this report, the GWP values were revised relative to the IPCC's *Second Assessment Report (SAR)* (IPCC 1996), IPCC's *Third Assessment Report (TAR)* (IPCC 2001), and the IPCC's *Fourth Assessment Report (AR4)* (IPCC 2007). Although the AR4 GWP values are used throughout this report in line with UNFCCC inventory reporting guidelines, it is informative to review the changes to the GWP values and the impact they have on the total GWP-weighted emissions of the United States. All GWP values use CO₂ as a reference gas; a change in

the radiative efficiency of CO₂ thus impacts the GWP of all other greenhouse gases. Since the SAR and TAR, the IPCC has applied an improved calculation of CO₂ radiative forcing and an improved CO₂ response function. The GWP values are drawn from IPCC (2007), with updates for those cases where new laboratory or radiative transfer results have been published. Additionally, the atmospheric lifetimes of some gases have been recalculated, and updated background concentrations were used. Table A-286 shows how the GWP values of the other gases relative to CO₂ tend to be larger in AR4 and AR5 because the revised radiative forcing of CO₂ is lower than in earlier assessments, taking into account revisions in lifetimes. Comparisons of GWP values are based on the 100-year time horizon required for UNFCCC inventory reporting. However, there were some instances in which other variables, such as the radiative efficiency or the chemical lifetime, were altered that resulted in further increases or decreases in particular GWP values. In addition, the values for radiative forcing and lifetimes have been calculated for a variety of halocarbons. Updates in some well-mixed HFC compounds (including HFC-23, HFC-32, HFC-134a, and HFC-227ea) for AR4 result from investigation into radiative efficiencies in these compounds, with some GWP values changing by up to 40 percent; with this change, the uncertainties associated with these well-mixed HFCs are thought to be approximately 12 percent.

It should be noted that the use of IPCC AR4 GWP values for the current Inventory applies across the entire time series of the Inventory (i.e., from 1990 to 2014). As such, GWP comparisons throughout this chapter are presented relative to AR4 GWPs.

Table A-286: Comparison of GWP values and Lifetimes Used in the SAR, AR4, and AR5

Gas	Lifetime (years)			GWP (100 year)				Difference in GWP (Relative to AR4)					
	SAR	AR4	AR5	SAR	AR4	AR5 ^a	AR5 with feedbacks ^b	SAR	SAR (%)	AR5 ^a	AR5 (%)	AR5 with feedbacks ^b	AR5 with feedbacks ^b (%)
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	^c	^d	^d	1	1	1	1	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
Methane (CH ₄) ^d	12±3	8.7/12 ^e	12.4	21	25	28	34	(4)	(16%)	3	12%	9	36%
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	120	120/114 ^e	121	310	298	265	298	12	4%	(33)	(11%)	0	0%
Hydrofluorocarbons													
HFC-23	264	270	222	11,700	14,800	12,400	13,856	(3,100)	(21%)	(2,400)	(16%)	(944)	(6)%
HFC-32	5.6	4.9	5.2	650	675	677	817	(25)	(4%)	2	+%	142	21%
HFC-125	32.6	29	28.2	2,800	3,500	3,170	3,691	(700)	(20%)	(330)	(9%)	191	5%
HFC-134a	14.6	14	13.4	1,300	1,430	1,300	1,549	(130)	(9%)	(130)	(9%)	119	8%
HFC-143a	48.3	52	47.1	3,800	4,470	4,800	5,508	(670)	(15%)	330	7%	1,038	23%
HFC-152a	1.5	1.4	1.5	140	124	138	167	16	13%	14	11%	43	35%
HFC-227ea	36.5	34.2	38.9	2,900	3,220	3,350	3,860	(320)	(10%)	130	4%	640	20%
HFC-236fa	209	240	242	6,300	9,810	8,060	8,998	(3,510)	(36%)	(1,750)	(18%)	(812)	(8)%
HFC-245fa	NA	7.6	7.7	NA	1,030	858	1032	NA	NA	(172)	(17%)	2	+%
HFC-365mfc	NA	6.6	8.7	NA	794	804	966	NA	NA	10	1%	172	22%
HFC-43-10mee	17.1	15.9	16.1	1,300	1,640	1,650	1,952	(340)	(21%)	10	1%	312	19%
Fully Fluorinated Species													
SF ₆	3,200	3,200	3,200	23,900	22,800	23,500	26,087	1,100	5%	700	3%	3,287	14%
CF ₄	50,000	50,000	50,000	6,500	7,390	6,630	7,349	(890)	(12%)	(760)	(10%)	(41)	(1)%
C ₂ F ₆	10,000	10,000	10,000	9,200	12,200	11,100	12,340	(3,000)	(25%)	(1,100)	(9%)	140	1%
C ₃ F ₈	2,600	2,600	2,600	7,000	8,830	8,900	9,878	(1,830)	(21%)	70	1%	1,048	12%
C ₄ F ₁₀	2,600	2,600	2,600	7,000	8,860	9,200	10,213	(1,860)	(21%)	340	4%	1,353	15%
c-C ₄ F ₈	3,200	3,200	3,200	8,700	10,300	9,540	10,592	(1,600)	(16%)	(760)	(7%)	292	3%
C ₅ F ₁₂	4,100	4,100	4,100	7,500	9,160	8,550	9,484	(1,660)	(18%)	(610)	(7%)	324	4%
C ₆ F ₁₄	3,200	3,200	3,100	7,400	9,300	7,910	8,780	(1,900)	(20%)	(1,390)	(15%)	(520)	(6)%
NF ₃	NA	740	500	NA	17,200	16,100	17,885	NA	NA	(1,100)	(6%)	685	4%

+ Does not exceed 0.05 or 0.05 percent.

NC (No Change)

NA (Not Applicable)

^a The GWP values presented here are the ones most consistent with the methodology used in the AR4 report.

^b The GWP values presented here from the AR5 report include climate-carbon feedbacks for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

^c For a given amount of carbon dioxide emitted, some fraction of the atmospheric increase in concentration is quickly absorbed by the oceans and terrestrial vegetation, some fraction of the atmospheric increase will only slowly decrease over a number of years, and a small portion of the increase will remain for many centuries or more.

^d No single lifetime can be determined for CO₂. (See IPCC 2001)

^e The methane GWP includes the direct effects and those indirect effects due to the production of tropospheric ozone and stratospheric water vapor. The indirect effect due to the production of CO₂ is only included in the value from AR5 that includes climate-carbon feedbacks.

^f Methane and nitrous oxide have chemical feedback systems that can alter the length of the atmospheric response, in these cases, global mean atmospheric lifetime (LT) is given first, followed by perturbation time (PT).

Note: Parentheses indicate negative values. Source: IPCC (2013), IPCC (2007), IPCC (2001), IPCC (1996).

The choice of GWP values between the SAR, AR4, and AR5 with or without climate-carbon feedbacks has an impact on both the overall emissions estimated by the Inventory, as well as the trend in emissions over time. To summarize, Table A-287 shows the overall trend in U.S. greenhouse gas emissions, by gas, from 1990 through 2014 using the four GWP sets. The table also presents the impact of SAR and AR5 GWP values with or without feedbacks on the total emissions for 1990 and for 2014.

Table A-287: Effects on U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using SAR, AR4, and AR5 GWP values (MMT CO₂Eq.)

Gas	Trend from 1990 to 2014				Revisions to Annual Emission Estimates (Relative to AR4)					
					1990			2014		
	SAR	AR4	AR5 ^a	AR5 ^b	SAR	AR5 ^a	AR5 ^b	SAR	AR5 ^a	AR5 ^b
CO ₂	440.9	440.9	440.9	440.9	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
CH ₄	(36.1)	(43.0)	(48.2)	(58.5)	(123.8)	92.9	278.6	(116.9)	87.7	263.1
N ₂ O	(2.8)	(2.7)	(2.4)	(2.7)	16.4	(45.0)	0.0	16.2	(44.7)	0.0
HFCs, PFCs, SF ₆ and NF ₃	60.8	78.1	71.3	88.3	(11.8)	(8.9)	1.6	(29.2)	(15.7)	11.7
Total	462.7	473.3	461.7	468.0	(119.3)	38.9	280.2	(129.9)	27.3	274.8
Percent Change	7.4%	7.4%	7.2%	7.0%	(1.9)%	0.6%	4.4%	(1.9)%	0.4%	4.0%

NC (No Change)

^a The GWP values presented here are the ones most consistent with the methodology used in the AR4 report, and exclude climate-carbon feedbacks.

^b The GWP values presented here from the AR5 report include climate-carbon feedbacks for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Excludes sinks. Parentheses indicate negative values.

When the GWP values from the SAR are applied to the emission estimates presented in this report, total emissions for the year 2014 are 6,740.6 MMT CO₂ Eq., as compared to the official emission estimate of 6,870.5 MMT CO₂ Eq. using AR4 GWP values (i.e., the use of SAR GWPs results in a 1.9 percent decrease relative to emissions estimated using AR4 GWPs). Table A-288 provides a detailed summary of U.S. greenhouse gas emissions and sinks for 1990 through 2014, using the GWP values from the SAR. The percent change in emissions is equal to the percent change in the GWP; however, in cases where multiple gases are emitted in varying amounts the percent change is variable over the years, such as with substitutes for ozone depleting substances. Table A-289 summarizes the resulting change in emissions from using SAR GWP values relative to emissions using AR4 values for 1990 through 2014, including the percent change for 2014.

Table A-288: Recent Trends in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Sinks using the SAR GWP values (MMT CO₂ Eq.)

Gas/Source	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CO₂	5,115.1	6,122.7	5,688.8	5,559.5	5,349.2	5,502.6	5,556.0
Fossil Fuel Combustion	4,740.7	5,747.1	5,358.3	5,227.7	5,024.7	5,157.6	5,208.2
<i>Electricity Generation</i>	1,820.8	2,400.9	2,258.4	2,157.7	2,022.2	2,038.1	2,039.3
<i>Transportation</i>	1,493.8	1,887.0	1,728.3	1,707.6	1,696.8	1,713.0	1,737.6
<i>Industrial</i>	842.5	828.0	775.5	773.3	782.9	812.2	813.3
<i>Residential</i>	338.3	357.8	334.6	326.8	282.5	329.7	345.1
<i>Commercial</i>	217.4	223.5	220.1	220.7	196.7	221.0	231.9
<i>U.S. Territories</i>	27.9	49.9	41.4	41.5	43.6	43.5	41.0
Non-Energy Use of Fuels	118.1	138.9	114.1	108.5	105.6	121.7	114.3
Iron and Steel Production & Metallurgical							
Coke Production	99.7	66.5	55.7	59.9	54.2	52.2	55.4
Natural Gas Systems	37.7	30.1	32.4	35.7	35.2	38.5	42.4
Cement Production	33.3	45.9	31.3	32.0	35.1	36.1	38.8
Petrochemical Production	21.6	27.4	27.2	26.3	26.5	26.4	26.5
Lime Production	11.7	14.6	13.4	14.0	13.7	14.0	14.1
Other Process Uses of Carbonates	4.9	6.3	9.6	9.3	8.0	10.4	12.1
Ammonia Production	13.0	9.2	9.2	9.3	9.4	10.0	9.4
Incineration of Waste	8.0	12.5	11.0	10.5	10.4	9.4	9.4
Carbon Dioxide Consumption	1.5	1.4	4.4	4.1	4.0	4.2	4.5

Urea Consumption for Non-Agricultural Purposes	3.8	3.7	4.7	4.0	4.4	4.2	4.0
Petroleum Systems	3.6	3.9	4.2	4.2	3.9	3.7	3.6
Aluminum Production	6.8	4.1	2.7	3.3	3.4	3.3	2.8
Soda Ash Production and Consumption	2.8	3.0	2.7	2.7	2.8	2.8	2.8
Ferroalloy Production	2.2	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.9	1.8	1.9
Titanium Dioxide Production	1.2	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.7	1.8
Glass Production	1.5	1.9	1.5	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.3
Phosphoric Acid Production	1.5	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.1
Zinc Production	0.6	1.0	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.0
Lead Production	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Silicon Carbide Production and Consumption	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Magnesium Production and Processing	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Wood Biomass and Ethanol Consumption ^a	219.4	229.8	265.1	268.1	267.7	286.3	293.7
International Bunker Fuels ^b	103.5	113.1	117.0	111.7	105.8	99.8	103.2
CH₄	650.0	602.6	606.8	602.6	600.1	606.0	613.9
Natural Gas Systems	173.7	149.0	139.6	142.9	145.0	147.5	147.9
Enteric Fermentation	137.9	141.8	143.9	141.9	140.1	139.0	138.0
Landfills	150.8	129.4	119.4	121.3	119.5	121.2	124.3
Petroleum Systems	32.5	41.0	45.4	47.3	49.0	54.4	57.2
Coal Mining	81.1	53.9	69.2	59.8	55.8	54.3	56.8
Manure Management	31.2	47.3	51.2	51.7	53.5	51.5	51.4
Wastewater Treatment	13.1	13.4	13.0	12.8	12.6	12.4	12.3
Rice Cultivation	11.0	10.9	10.0	9.9	10.0	10.0	10.0
Stationary Combustion	7.1	6.2	5.9	5.9	5.6	6.7	6.8
Abandoned Underground Coal Mines	6.0	5.5	5.5	5.4	5.2	5.2	5.3
Composting	0.3	1.6	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.7
Mobile Combustion	4.7	2.3	1.9	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.7
Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Petrochemical Production	0.2	0.1	+	+	0.1	0.1	0.1
Ferroalloy Production	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Silicon Carbide Production and Consumption	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Iron and Steel Production & Metallurgical Coke Production	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Incineration of Waste	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
International Bunker Fuels ^b	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
N₂O	422.6	413.6	426.8	433.3	425.8	419.6	419.8
Agricultural Soil Management	315.5	309.1	333.6	336.1	336.1	331.5	331.2
Stationary Combustion	12.4	21.0	23.1	22.2	22.2	23.8	24.4
Manure Management	14.6	17.2	17.9	18.1	18.2	18.2	18.2
Mobile Combustion	42.9	35.8	24.6	23.3	20.8	18.9	17.0
Nitric Acid Production	12.6	11.8	12.0	11.3	10.9	11.1	11.4
Adipic Acid Production	15.8	7.4	4.4	10.6	5.8	4.1	5.7
Wastewater Treatment	3.5	4.5	4.7	4.9	4.9	5.0	5.0
N ₂ O from Product Uses	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4
Composting	0.4	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.9
Incineration of Waste	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Semiconductor Manufacture	+	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
International Bunker Fuels ^b	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.9
HFCs	36.9	102.2	126.2	129.5	130.3	132.3	138.2
Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances ^c	0.3	86.2	119.7	122.4	125.8	128.8	133.9
HFC-22 Production	36.4	15.8	6.4	6.9	4.3	3.2	4.0
Semiconductor Manufacture	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2
Magnesium Production and Processing	+	+	+	+	+	0.1	0.1
PFCs	20.6	5.5	3.7	5.8	5.3	4.8	5.0
Semiconductor Manufacture	18.4	3.0	1.6	2.9	2.8	2.5	2.5
Aluminum Production	2.2	2.6	2.1	2.9	2.5	2.3	2.5
SF₆	32.6	14.7	9.9	10.5	7.9	7.6	7.7

Electrical Transmission and Distribution	26.6	11.1	7.4	7.1	5.8	5.7	5.9
Magnesium Production and Processing	5.4	2.9	2.2	2.9	1.7	1.5	1.1
Semiconductor Manufacture	0.5	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.8
NF₃	NA						
Semiconductor Manufacture	NA						
Total Emissions	6,277.9	7,261.4	6,862.3	6,741.2	6,518.7	6,672.9	6,740.6
LULUCF Emissions^d	14.7	27.0	17.5	22.1	31.0	23.2	23.7
LULUCF Total Net Flux^e	(753.0)	(726.7)	(784.3)	(784.9)	(782.0)	(783.7)	(787.0)
LULUCF Sector Total^f	(738.3)	(699.7)	(766.7)	(762.8)	(751.0)	(760.4)	(763.3)
Net Emissions (Sources and Sinks)	5,539.5	6,561.7	6,095.5	5,978.5	5,767.7	5,912.4	5,977.2

+ Does not exceed 0.05 MMT CO₂ Eq.

Note: Total emissions presented without LULUCF. Net emissions presented with LULUCF.

^a Emissions from Wood Biomass and Ethanol Consumption are not included specifically in summing energy sector totals. Net carbon fluxes from changes in biogenic carbon reservoirs are accounted for in the estimates for Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry.

^b Emissions from International Bunker Fuels are not included in totals.

^c Small amounts of PFC emissions also result from this source.

^d LULUCF emissions include the CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O emissions reported for Non-CO₂ Emissions from Forest Fires, N₂O Fluxes from Forest Soils, CO₂ Emissions from Agricultural Liming, CO₂ Emissions from Urea Fertilization, Peatlands Remaining Peatlands, and N₂O Fluxes from Settlement Soils.

^e Net CO₂ flux is the net C stock change from the following categories: *Forest Land Remaining Forest Land, Land Converted to Forest Land, Cropland Remaining Cropland, Land Converted to Cropland, Grassland Remaining Grassland, Land Converted to Grassland, Settlements Remaining Settlements, and Other.*

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate net sequestration.

Table A-289: Change in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using SAR GWP values relative to AR4 GWP values (MMT CO₂ Eq.)

Gas/Source								Percent
	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Change in 2014
CO₂	NC							
CH₄	(123.8)	(114.8)	(115.6)	(114.8)	(114.3)	(115.4)	(116.9)	(8.0%)
Natural Gas Systems	(33.1)	(28.4)	(26.6)	(27.2)	(27.6)	(28.1)	(28.2)	(8.0%)
Enteric Fermentation	(26.3)	(27.0)	(27.4)	(27.0)	(26.7)	(26.5)	(26.3)	(8.0%)
Landfills	(28.7)	(24.6)	(22.7)	(23.1)	(22.8)	(23.1)	(23.7)	(8.0%)
Petroleum Systems	(6.2)	(7.8)	(8.7)	(9.0)	(9.3)	(10.4)	(10.9)	(8.0%)
Coal Mining	(15.4)	(10.3)	(13.2)	(11.4)	(10.6)	(10.3)	(10.8)	(8.0%)
Manure Management	(5.9)	(9.0)	(9.7)	(9.8)	(10.2)	(9.8)	(9.8)	(8.0%)
Wastewater Treatment	(2.5)	(2.5)	(2.5)	(2.4)	(2.4)	(2.4)	(2.4)	(8.0%)
Rice Cultivation	(2.1)	(2.1)	(1.9)	(1.9)	(1.9)	(1.9)	(1.9)	(8.0%)
Stationary Combustion	(1.4)	(1.2)	(1.1)	(1.1)	(1.1)	(1.3)	(1.3)	(8.0%)
Abandoned Underground Coal Mines	(1.2)	(1.1)	(1.1)	(1.0)	(1.0)	(1.0)	(1.0)	(8.0%)
Composting	(0.1)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(8.0%)
Mobile Combustion	(0.9)	(0.4)	(0.4)	(0.4)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(0.3)	(8.0%)
Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
Petrochemical Production	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
Ferroalloy Production	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
Silicon Carbide Production and Consumption	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
Iron and Steel Production & Metallurgical Coke Production	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
Incineration of Waste	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
<i>International Bunker Fuels^a</i>	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(8.0%)
N₂O	16.4	16.0	16.5	16.8	16.5	16.2	16.2	(0.7%)
Agricultural Soil Management	12.2	12.0	12.9	13.0	13.0	12.8	12.8	(0.7%)
Stationary Combustion	0.5	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	(0.7%)
Manure Management	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	(0.7%)
Mobile Combustion	1.7	1.4	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	(0.7%)
Nitric Acid Production	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	(0.7%)
Adipic Acid Production	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	(0.7%)

Wastewater Treatment	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	(0.7%)
N ₂ O from Product Uses	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	(0.7%)
Composting	+	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	(0.7%)
Incineration of Waste	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	(0.7%)
Semiconductor Manufacture	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	(0.7%)
Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	(0.7%)
<i>International Bunker Fuels^a</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	(0.7%)
HFCs	(9.7)	(17.7)	(23.2)	(24.8)	(25.5)	(26.7)	(28.5)	(10.1%)
Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances ^b	0.0	(13.5)	(21.5)	(22.9)	(24.3)	(25.8)	(27.3)	(9.8%)
HCFC-22 Production	(9.7)	(4.2)	(1.7)	(1.8)	(1.1)	(0.9)	(1.1)	(18.9%)
Semiconductor Manufacture	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(0.1)	(18.9%)
Magnesium Production and Processing	+	+	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(23.1%)
PFCs	(3.6)	(1.1)	(0.8)	(1.2)	(0.7)	(1.0)	(0.6)	(9.5%)
Semiconductor Manufacture	15.6	(0.3)	(1.1)	(0.6)	(0.2)	(0.4)	(0.5)	(12.4%)
Aluminum Production	(19.2)	(0.9)	0.3	(0.6)	(0.4)	(0.6)	+	(6.1%)
SF₆	1.5	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	(2.6%)
Electrical Transmission and Distribution	1.2	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	(2.6%)
Magnesium Production and Processing	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	+	(2.6%)
Semiconductor Manufacture	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	(2.6%)
NF₃	NA	(37.2%)						
Semiconductor Manufacture	NA	(37.2%)						
Total Emissions	(78.7)	(76.3)	(77.4)	(77.9)	(76.8)	(77.7)	(78.8)	(1.8%)

NC (No Change)

NA (Not Applicable)

+ Absolute value does not exceed 0.05 MMT CO₂ Eq.

^aEmissions from International Bunker Fuels are not included in totals.

^bSmall amounts of PFC emissions also result from this source.

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Table A-290 below shows a comparison of total emissions estimates by sector using both the IPCC SAR and AR4 GWP values. For most sectors, the change in emissions that result from using SAR relative to AR4 GWP values was minimal. The effect on emissions from waste was by far the greatest (15.2 percent decrease in 2014 using SAR GWP values, relative to emissions using AR4 GWP values), due the predominance of CH₄ emissions in this sector. Emissions from all other sectors were comprised of mainly CO₂ or a mix of gases, which moderated the effect of the changes.

Table A-290: Comparison of Emissions by Sector using IPCC AR4 and SAR GWP Values (MMT CO₂Eq.)

Sector	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Energy							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	5,324.9	6,294.5	5,884.6	5,744.0	5,533.9	5,693.5	5,746.2
SAR GWP	5,269.0	6,247.6	5,835.5	5,695.6	5,485.6	5,643.8	5,695.3
Difference (%)	(1.1%)	(0.7%)	(0.8%)	(0.8%)	(0.9%)	(0.9%)	(0.9%)
Industrial Processes and Product Use							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	340.9	354.3	353.0	370.5	360.1	363.5	379.2
SAR GWP	330.3	336.5	329.6	345.3	334.4	336.3	350.8
Difference (%)	(3.1%)	(5.0%)	(6.6%)	(6.8%)	(7.1%)	(7.5%)	(7.5%)
Agriculture							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	532.0	552.2	582.3	583.1	583.3	575.3	573.6
SAR GWP	510.5	526.7	556.8	558.0	558.2	550.5	549.1
Difference (%)	(4.1%)	(4.6%)	(4.4%)	(4.3%)	(4.3%)	(4.3%)	(4.3%)
LULUCF							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	(738.0)	(698.5)	(766.4)	(762.0)	(749.7)	(759.6)	(762.5)
SAR GWP	(738.3)	(699.7)	(766.7)	(762.8)	(751.0)	(760.4)	(763.3)
Difference (%)	0.1%	0.2%	+	0.1%	0.2%	0.1%	0.1%
Waste							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	199.3	177.8	165.5	167.8	165.7	167.8	171.4
SAR GWP	168.1	150.6	140.3	142.3	140.5	142.3	145.3
Difference (%)	(15.6%)	(15.3%)	(15.3%)	(15.2%)	(15.2%)	(15.2%)	(15.2%)
Net Emissions							
AR4 GWP, Used In Inventory	5,659.2	6,680.3	6,219.0	6,103.4	5,893.3	6,040.4	6,108.0
SAR GWP	5,539.5	6,561.7	6,095.5	5,978.5	5,767.7	5,912.4	5,977.2

Difference (%) (2.1%) (1.8%) (2.0%) (2.0%) (2.1%) (2.1%) (2.1%)

+ Does not exceed 0.05 percent.

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Further, Table A-291 and Table A-292 show the comparison of emission estimates using AR5 GWP values relative to AR4 GWP values without climate-carbon feedbacks, on an emissions and percent change basis. Table A-293 and Table A-294 show the comparison of emission estimates using AR5 GWP values with climate-carbon feedbacks. The use of AR5 GWP values without climate-carbon feedbacks¹²² results in an increase in emissions of CH₄ and SF₆ relative to AR4 GWP values, but a decrease in emissions of other gases. The use of AR5 GWP values with climate-carbon feedbacks does not impact N₂O emissions; however, it results in an increase in emissions of CH₄ and SF₆ relative to AR4 GWP values, and a decrease in emissions of other gases. Overall, these comparisons of AR4 and AR5 GWP values do not have a significant effect on U.S. emission trends, resulting in an increase in emissions of less than 1 percent using AR5 GWP values, or 4 percent when using AR5 GWP values with climate-carbon feedbacks. As with the comparison of SAR and AR4 GWP values presented above, the percent change in emissions is equal to the percent change in the GWP for each gas; however, in cases where multiple gases are emitted in varying amounts the percent change is variable over the years, such as with substitutes for ozone depleting substances.

Table A-291: Change in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using AR5^a without Climate-Carbon Feedbacks Relative to AR4 GWP Values (MMT CO₂ Eq.)

Gas	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CO ₂	NC						
CH ₄	92.9	86.1	86.7	86.1	85.7	86.6	87.7
N ₂ O	(45.0)	(44.0)	(45.4)	(46.1)	(45.3)	(44.7)	(44.7)
HFCs	(7.5)	(13.4)	(14.7)	(15.0)	(14.8)	(14.9)	(15.8)
PFCs	(2.4)	(0.6)	(0.4)	(0.7)	(0.2)	(0.6)	(0.2)
SF ₆	1.0	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2
NF ₃	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Total	38.9	28.4	26.4	24.5	25.5	26.6	27.3

+ Does not exceed 0.05 MMT CO₂ Eq.

NC (No change)

Note: Total emissions presented without LULUCF.

^a The GWP values presented here are the ones most consistent with the methodology used in the AR4 report. The AR5 report has also calculated GWP values (shown in Table A-293) where climate-carbon feedbacks have been included for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Table A-292: Change in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using AR5^a without Climate-Carbon Feedbacks Relative to AR4 GWP Values (Percent)

Gas/Source	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CO ₂	NC						
CH ₄	12.0%	12.0%	12.0%	12.0%	12.0%	12.0%	12.0%
N ₂ O	(11.1%)	(11.1%)	(11.1%)	(11.1%)	(11.1%)	(11.1%)	(11.1%)
HFCs	(16.0%)	(11.2%)	(9.8%)	(9.7%)	(9.5%)	(9.4%)	(9.4%)
Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances	11.3%	(10.2%)	(9.4%)	(9.3%)	(9.3%)	(9.2%)	(9.2%)
HCFC-22 Production ^a	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)
Semiconductor Manufacture ^b	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)	(16.2%)
Magnesium Production and Processing ^c	0.0%	0.0%	(9.1%)	(9.1%)	(9.1%)	(9.1%)	(9.1%)
PFCs	(10.0%)	(9.6%)	(9.4%)	(9.4%)	(3.7%)	(10.2%)	(3.3%)
Semiconductor Manufacture ^b	(9.4%)	(9.1%)	(9.1%)	(8.9%)	(9.1%)	(9.1%)	(9.2%)

¹²² The IPCC AR5 report provides additional information on emission metrics. See <https://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/wg1/WG1AR5_Chapter08_FINAL.pdf>.

Aluminum Production ^d	(10.1%)	(10.1%)	(10.0%)	(10.0%)	2.0%	(11.2%)	3.8%
SF ₆	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%
NF ₃	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)
Total	0.6%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%

Note: Total emissions presented without LULUCF.

NC (No change)

^a The GWP values presented here are the ones most consistent with the methodology used in the AR4 report. The AR5 report has also calculated GWP values (shown in Table A-294) where climate-carbon feedbacks have been included for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

^a HFC-23 emitted

^b Emissions from HFC-23, CF₄, C₂F₆, C₃F₈, SF₆, and NF₃.

^c Zero change in beginning of time series since emissions were zero.

^d PFC emissions from CF₄ and C₂F₆

Note: Parentheses indicate negative values.

Table A-293: Change in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using AR5 with Climate-Carbon Feedbacks^a Relative to AR4 GWP Values (MMT CO₂ Eq.)

Gas	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CO ₂	NC						
CH ₄	278.6	258.2	260.1	258.3	257.2	259.7	263.1
N ₂ O	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HFCs	(2.9)	5.0	8.9	9.1	9.6	10.0	10.2
PFCs	(+)	+	+	+	0.4	(+)	0.4
SF ₆	4.5	2.0	1.4	1.4	1.1	1.0	1.1
NF ₃	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Total	280.2	265.3	270.4	268.9	268.4	270.8	274.8

Note: Total emissions presented without LULUCF.

NC (No Change)

+ Absolute value does not exceed 0.05 MMT CO₂ Eq.

^a The GWP values presented here from the AR5 report include climate-carbon feedbacks for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Table A-294: Change in U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Using AR5 with Climate-Carbon Feedbacks^a Relative to AR4 GWP Values (Percent)

Gas/Source	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CO ₂	NC						
CH ₄	36.0%	36.0%	36.0%	36.0%	36.0%	36.0%	36.0%
N ₂ O	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
HFCs	(6.1%)	4.2%	6.0%	5.9%	6.2%	6.3%	6.1%
Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances	34.7%	6.3%	6.7%	6.7%	6.7%	6.6%	6.6%
HFC-22 Production ^a	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)
Semiconductor Manufacture ^b	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)	(6.4%)
Magnesium Production and Processing ^c	0.0%	0.0%	8.3%	8.3%	8.3%	8.3%	8.3%
PFCs	(0.2%)	0.3%	0.5%	0.5%	6.9%	(0.3%)	7.3%
Semiconductor Manufacture ^b	0.6%	0.9%	0.9%	1.1%	0.9%	0.9%	0.8%
Aluminum Production ^d	(0.3%)	(0.3%)	(0.1%)	(0.2%)	13.2%	(1.5%)	15.1%
SF ₆	14.4%	14.4%	14.4%	14.4%	14.4%	14.4%	14.4%
NF ₃	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%
Total	4.4%	3.6%	3.9%	3.9%	4.0%	4.0%	4.0%

Note: Total emissions presented without LULUCF.

NC (No Change)

^a The GWP values presented here from the AR5 report include climate-carbon feedbacks for the non-CO₂ gases in order to be consistent with the approach used in calculating the CO₂ lifetime. Additionally, the AR5 reported separate values for fossil versus biogenic methane in order to account for the CO₂ oxidation product.

^a HFC-23 emitted

^b Emissions from HFC-23, CF₄, C₂F₆, C₃F₈, SF₆, and NF₃.

^c Zero change in beginning of time series since emissions were zero.

^d PFC emissions from CF₄ and C₂F₆

Notes: Excludes Sinks. Parentheses indicate negative values.

6.2. Ozone Depleting Substance Emissions

Ozone is present in both the stratosphere,¹²³ where it shields the earth from harmful levels of ultraviolet radiation, and at lower concentrations in the troposphere,¹²⁴ where it is the main component of anthropogenic photochemical “smog.” Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), halons, carbon tetrachloride, methyl chloroform, and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), along with certain other chlorine and bromine containing compounds, have been found to deplete the ozone levels in the stratosphere. These compounds are commonly referred to as ozone depleting substances (ODSs). If left unchecked, stratospheric ozone depletion could result in a dangerous increase of ultraviolet radiation reaching the earth’s surface. In 1987, nations around the world signed the *Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer*. This landmark agreement created an international framework for limiting, and ultimately eliminating, the production of most ozone depleting substances. ODSs have historically been used in a variety of industrial applications, including refrigeration and air conditioning, foam blowing, fire extinguishing, sterilization, solvent cleaning, and as an aerosol propellant.

In the United States, the Clean Air Act Amendments of 1990 provide the legal instrument for implementation of the *Montreal Protocol* controls. The Clean Air Act classifies ozone depleting substances as either Class I or Class II, depending upon the ozone depletion potential (ODP) of the compound.¹²⁵ The production of CFCs, halons, carbon tetrachloride, and methyl chloroform – all Class I substances – has already ended in the United States. However, large amounts of these chemicals remain in existing equipment,¹²⁶ and stockpiles of the ODSs, as well as material recovered from equipment being decommissioned, are used for maintaining the existing equipment. As a result, emissions of Class I compounds will continue, albeit in ever decreasing amounts, for many more years. Class II designated substances, all of which are HCFCs, have been, or are being, phased out at later dates than Class I compounds because they have lower ozone depletion potentials. These compounds served, and in some cases continue to serve, as interim replacements for Class I compounds in many industrial applications. The use and emissions of HCFCs in the United States is anticipated to continue for several decades as equipment that use Class II substances are retired from use. Under current controls, however, the production for domestic use of all HCFCs in the United States will end by the year 2030.

In addition to contributing to ozone depletion, CFCs, halons, carbon tetrachloride, methyl chloroform, and HCFCs are also potent greenhouse gases. However, the depletion of the ozone layer has a cooling effect on the climate that counteracts the direct warming from tropospheric emissions of ODSs. Stratospheric ozone influences the earth’s radiative balance by absorption and emission of longwave radiation from the troposphere as well as absorption of shortwave radiation from the sun; overall, stratospheric ozone has a warming effect.

The IPCC has prepared both direct GWP values and net (combined direct warming and indirect cooling) GWP ranges for some of the most common ozone depleting substances (IPCC 2007). See Annex 6.1, Global Warming Potential Values, for a listing of the net GWP values for ODS.

Although the IPCC emission inventory guidelines do not require the reporting of emissions of ozone depleting substances, the United States believes that no inventory is complete without the inclusion of these compounds. Emission estimates for several ozone depleting substances are provided in Table A-295.

Table A-295: Emissions of Ozone Depleting Substances (kt)

Compound	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Class I							
CFC-11	29	12	8	8	8	7	7
CFC-12	124	23	3	3	2	2	1
CFC-113	59	+	+	+	+	+	+
CFC-114	5	+	+	+	+	+	+
CFC-115	8	2	+	+	+	+	+
Carbon Tetrachloride	4	+	+	+	+	+	+

¹²³ The stratosphere is the layer from the top of the troposphere up to about 50 kilometers. Approximately 90 percent of atmospheric ozone is within the stratosphere. The greatest concentration of ozone occurs in the middle of the stratosphere, in a region commonly called the ozone layer.

¹²⁴ The troposphere is the layer from the ground up to about 11 kilometers near the poles and 16 kilometers in equatorial regions (i.e., the lowest layer of the atmosphere, where humans live). It contains roughly 80 percent of the mass of all gases in the atmosphere and is the site for weather processes including most of the water vapor and clouds.

¹²⁵ Substances with an ozone depletion potential of 0.2 or greater are designated as Class I. All other designated substances that deplete stratospheric ozone but which have an ODP of less than 0.2 are Class II.

¹²⁶ Older refrigeration and air-conditioning equipment, fire extinguishing systems, meter-dose inhalers, and foam products blown with CFCs/HCFCs may still contain ODS.

Methyl Chloroform	223	+	+	+	+	+	+
Halon-1211	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Halon-1301	2	+	+	+	+	+	+
Class II							
HCFC-22	49	82	82	80	76	73	69
HCFC-123	+	1	1	1	1	1	1
HCFC-124	+	2	1	1	1	1	1
HCFC-141b	1	4	9	9	9	10	10
HCFC-142b	2	3	1	1	1	1	1
HCFC-225ca/cb	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

+ Does not exceed 0.5 kt.

Methodology and Data Sources

Emissions of ozone depleting substances were estimated using the EPA's Vintaging Model. The model, named for its method of tracking the emissions of annual "vintages" of new equipment that enter into service, is a "bottom-up" model. It models the consumption of chemicals based on estimates of the quantity of equipment or products sold, serviced, and retired each year, and the amount of the chemical required to manufacture and/or maintain the equipment. The Vintaging Model makes use of this market information to build an inventory of the in-use stocks of the equipment in each of the end-uses. Emissions are estimated by applying annual leak rates, service emission rates, and disposal emission rates to each population of equipment. By aggregating the emission and consumption output from the different end-uses, the model produces estimates of total annual use and emissions of each chemical. Please see Annex 3.9, Methodology for Estimating HFC and PFC Emissions from Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances, of this Inventory for a more detailed discussion of the Vintaging Model.

Uncertainties

Uncertainties exist with regard to the levels of chemical production, equipment sales, equipment characteristics, and end-use emissions profiles that are used by these models. Please see the ODS Substitutes section of this report for a more detailed description of the uncertainties that exist in the Vintaging Model.

6.3. Sulfur Dioxide Emissions

Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), emitted into the atmosphere through natural and anthropogenic processes, affects the Earth's radiative budget through photochemical transformation into sulfate aerosols that can (1) scatter sunlight back to space, thereby reducing the radiation reaching the Earth's surface; (2) affect cloud formation; and (3) affect atmospheric chemical composition (e.g., stratospheric ozone, by providing surfaces for heterogeneous chemical reactions). The overall effect of SO₂-derived aerosols on radiative forcing is believed to be negative (IPCC 2007). However, because SO₂ is short-lived and unevenly distributed through the atmosphere, its radiative forcing impacts are highly uncertain. Sulfur dioxide emissions have been provided below in Table A-296.

The major source of SO₂ emissions in the United States is the burning of sulfur containing fuels, mainly coal. Metal smelting and other industrial processes also release significant quantities of SO₂. The largest contributor to U.S. emissions of SO₂ is electricity generation, accounting for 64.0 percent of total SO₂ emissions in 2014 (see Table A-297); coal combustion accounted for approximately 92.0 percent of that total. The second largest source was industrial fuel combustion, which produced 13.3 percent of 2014 SO₂ emissions. Overall, SO₂ emissions in the United States decreased by 78.4 percent from 1990 to 2014. The majority of this decline came from reductions from electricity generation, primarily due to increased consumption of low sulfur coal from surface mines in western states.

Sulfur dioxide is important for reasons other than its effect on radiative forcing. It is a major contributor to the formation of urban smog and acid rain. As a contributor to urban smog, high concentrations of SO₂ can cause significant increases in acute and chronic respiratory diseases. In addition, once SO₂ is emitted, it is chemically transformed in the atmosphere and returns to earth as the primary contributor to acid deposition, or acid rain. Acid rain has been found to accelerate the decay of building materials and paints, cause the acidification of lakes and streams, and damage trees. As a result of these harmful effects, the United States has regulated the emissions of SO₂ under the Clean Air Act. The EPA has also developed a strategy to control these emissions via four programs: (1) the National Ambient Air Quality Standards program,¹²⁷ (2) New Source Performance Standards,¹²⁸ (3) the New Source Review/Prevention of Significant Deterioration Program,¹²⁹ and (4) the Sulfur Dioxide Allowance Program.¹³⁰

Table A-296: SO₂ Emissions (kt)

Sector/Source	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Energy	19,628	12,364	6,396	5,273	4,106	4,020	3,923
Stationary Sources	18,407	11,541	6,120	5,008	3,859	3,790	3,710
Oil and Gas Activities	390	180	117	108	108	108	108
Mobile Sources	793	619	144	142	125	108	90
Waste Combustion	38	25	16	15	15	15	15
Industrial Processes and Product Use	1,307	831	617	604	604	604	604
Miscellaneous	11	114	146	179	179	179	179
Other Industrial Processes	362	327	190	171	171	171	171
Metals Processing	659	158	141	131	131	131	131
Chemical and Allied Product							
Manufacturing	269	228	132	115	115	115	115
Storage and Transport	6	2	7	8	8	8	8
Solvent Use	0	+	+	+	+	+	+
Degreasing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Graphic Arts	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dry Cleaning	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0
Surface Coating	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other Industrial	0	+	+	+	+	+	+
Nonindustrial	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Agriculture	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Agricultural Burning	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Waste	+	1	+	+	+	+	+
Landfills	+	1	+	+	+	+	+
Wastewater Treatment	+	0	0	0	0	0	0

¹²⁷ [42 U.S.C § 7409, CAA § 109]

¹²⁸ [42 U.S.C § 7411, CAA § 111]

¹²⁹ [42 U.S.C § 7473, CAA § 163]

¹³⁰ [42 U.S.C § 7651, CAA § 401]

Miscellaneous	+	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Total		20,935	13,196	7,014	5,877	4,711	4,625	4,528

+ Does not exceed 0.5 kt* Miscellaneous includes other combustion and fugitive dust categories.

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.

Source: Data taken from EPA (2015) and disaggregated based on EPA (2003).

Table A-297: SO₂ Emissions from Electricity Generation (kt)

Fuel Type	1990	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Coal	13,808	8,680	4,752	3,859	2,802	2,739	2,665
Oil	580	458	251	204	148	144	141
Gas	1	174	95	77	56	55	53
Misc. Internal Combustion	45	57	31	25	18	18	18
Other	NA	71	39	31	23	22	22
Total	14,433	9,439	5,168	4,196	3,047	2,978	2,898

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.

Source: Data taken from EPA (2015) and disaggregated based on EPA (2003).

6.4. Complete List of Source Categories

Chapter/Source	Gas(es)
Energy	
Fossil Fuel Combustion	CO ₂
Non-Energy Use of Fossil Fuels	CO ₂
Stationary Combustion (excluding CO ₂)	CH ₄ , N ₂ O, CO, NO _x , NMVOC
Mobile Combustion (excluding CO ₂)	CH ₄ , N ₂ O, CO, NO _x , NMVOC
Coal Mining	CH ₄
Abandoned Underground Coal Mines	CH ₄
Petroleum Systems	CH ₄
Natural Gas Systems	CH ₄
Incineration of Waste	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO _x , CO, NMVOC
Industrial Processes and Product Use	
Titanium Dioxide Production	CO ₂
Aluminum Production	CO ₂ , CF ₄ , C ₂ F ₆
Iron and Steel Production & Metallurgical Coke Production	CO ₂ , CH ₄
Ferroalloy Production	CO ₂ , CH ₄
Ammonia Production	CO ₂
Urea Consumption for Non-Agricultural Purposes	CO ₂
Cement Production	CO ₂
Lime Production	CO ₂
Other Process Uses of Carbonates	CO ₂
Soda Ash Production and Consumption	CO ₂
Glass Production	CO ₂
Carbon Dioxide Consumption	CO ₂
Phosphoric Acid Production	CO ₂
Petrochemical Production	CH ₄ , CO ₂
Silicon Carbide Production and Consumption	CH ₄ , CO ₂
Lead Production	CO ₂
Zinc Production	CO ₂
Adipic Acid Production	N ₂ O
Nitric Acid Production	N ₂ O
N ₂ O from Product Uses	N ₂ O
Substitution of Ozone Depleting Substances	HFCs, PFCs ^a
HFC-22 Production	HFC-23
Semiconductor Manufacture	N ₂ O, HFCs, PFCs ^b , SF ₆ , NF ₃
Electrical Transmission and Distributing	SF ₆
Magnesium Production and Processing	CO ₂ , HFCs, SF ₆
Agriculture	
Enteric Fermentation	CH ₄
Manure Management	CH ₄ , N ₂ O
Rice Cultivation	CH ₄
Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO _x , CO
Agricultural Soil Management	N ₂ O
Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry	
Net CO ₂ Flux	CO ₂ (sink)
Cropland Remaining Cropland	CO ₂
Land Converted to Cropland	CO ₂
Grassland Remaining Grassland	CO ₂
Land Converted to Grassland	CO ₂
Settlements Remaining Settlements	CO ₂ , N ₂ O
Forest Land Remaining Forest Land	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO _x , CO
Land Converted to Forest Land	CO ₂
Wetlands Remaining Wetlands	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O
Other (Landfilled Yard Trimmings and Food Scraps)	CO ₂
Waste	
Landfills	CH ₄ , NO _x , CO, NMVOC
Wastewater Treatment	CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO _x , CO, NMVOC
Composting	CH ₄ , N ₂ O

^a Includes HFC-23, HFC-32, HFC-125, HFC-134a, HFC-143a, HFC-236fa, CF₄, HFC-152a, HFC-227ea, HFC-245fa, HFC-4310mee, and PFC/PPFes.

^b Includes such gases as HFC-23, CF₄, C₂F₆.

6.5. Constants, Units, and Conversions

Metric Prefixes

Although most activity data for the United States is gathered in customary U.S. units, these units are converted into metric units per international reporting guidelines. Table A-298 provides a guide for determining the magnitude of metric units.

Table A-298: Guide to Metric Unit Prefixes

Prefix/Symbol	Factor
atto (a)	10^{-18}
femto (f)	10^{-15}
pico (p)	10^{-12}
nano (n)	10^{-9}
micro (μ)	10^{-6}
milli (m)	10^{-3}
centi (c)	10^{-2}
deci (d)	10^{-1}
deca (da)	10
hecto (h)	10^2
kilo (k)	10^3
mega (M)	10^6
giga (G)	10^9
tera (T)	10^{12}
peta (P)	10^{15}
exa (E)	10^{18}

Unit Conversions

1 kilogram	=	2.205 pounds		
1 pound	=	0.454 kilograms		
1 short ton	=	2,000 pounds	=	0.9072 metric tons
1 metric ton	=	1,000 kilograms	=	1.1023 short tons

1 cubic meter	=	35.315 cubic feet
1 cubic foot	=	0.02832 cubic meters
1 U.S. gallon	=	3.785412 liters
1 barrel (bbl)	=	0.159 cubic meters
1 barrel (bbl)	=	42 U.S. gallons
1 liter	=	0.001 cubic meters

1 foot	=	0.3048 meters
1 meter	=	3.28 feet
1 mile	=	1.609 kilometers
1 kilometer	=	0.622 miles

1 acre	=	43,560 square feet	=	0.4047 hectares	=	4,047 square meters
1 square mile	=	2.589988 square kilometers				

To convert degrees Fahrenheit to degrees Celsius, subtract 32 and multiply by 5/9

To convert degrees Celsius to Kelvin, add 273.15 to the number of Celsius degrees

Density Conversions¹³¹

Methane	1 cubic meter	=	0.67606 kilograms
Carbon dioxide	1 cubic meter	=	1.85387 kilograms
Natural gas liquids	1 metric ton	=	11.6 barrels = 1,844.2 liters
Unfinished oils	1 metric ton	=	7.46 barrels = 1,186.04 liters
Alcohol	1 metric ton	=	7.94 barrels = 1,262.36 liters
Liquefied petroleum gas	1 metric ton	=	11.6 barrels = 1,844.2 liters
Aviation gasoline	1 metric ton	=	8.9 barrels = 1,415.0 liters
Naphtha jet fuel	1 metric ton	=	8.27 barrels = 1,314.82 liters
Kerosene jet fuel	1 metric ton	=	7.93 barrels = 1,260.72 liters
Motor gasoline	1 metric ton	=	8.53 barrels = 1,356.16 liters
Kerosene	1 metric ton	=	7.73 barrels = 1,228.97 liters
Naphtha	1 metric ton	=	8.22 barrels = 1,306.87 liters
Distillate	1 metric ton	=	7.46 barrels = 1,186.04 liters
Residual oil	1 metric ton	=	6.66 barrels = 1,058.85 liters
Lubricants	1 metric ton	=	7.06 barrels = 1,122.45 liters
Bitumen	1 metric ton	=	6.06 barrels = 963.46 liters
Waxes	1 metric ton	=	7.87 barrels = 1,251.23 liters
Petroleum coke	1 metric ton	=	5.51 barrels = 876.02 liters
Petrochemical feedstocks	1 metric ton	=	7.46 barrels = 1,186.04 liters
Special naphtha	1 metric ton	=	8.53 barrels = 1,356.16 liters
Miscellaneous products	1 metric ton	=	8.00 barrels = 1,271.90 liters

Energy Conversions

Converting Various Energy Units to Joules

The common energy unit used in international reports of greenhouse gas emissions is the joule. A joule is the energy required to push with a force of one Newton for one meter. A terajoule (TJ) is one trillion (10^{12}) joules. A British thermal unit (Btu, the customary U.S. energy unit) is the quantity of heat required to raise the temperature of one pound of water one degree Fahrenheit at or near 39.2 degrees Fahrenheit.

1 TJ =	2.388×10 ¹¹ calories
	23.88 metric tons of crude oil equivalent
	947.8 million Btus
	277,800 kilowatt-hours

Converting Various Physical Units to Energy Units

Data on the production and consumption of fuels are first gathered in physical units. These units must be converted to their energy equivalents. The conversion factors in Table A-299 can be used as default factors, if local data are not available. See Appendix A of EIA's *Monthly Energy Review February 2016* (EIA 2016) for more detailed information on the energy content of various fuels.

¹³¹ Reference: EIA (2007)

Table A-299: Conversion Factors to Energy Units (Heat Equivalents)

Fuel Type (Units)	Factor
Solid Fuels (Million Btu/Short ton)	
Anthracite coal	22.573
Bituminous coal	23.89
Sub-bituminous coal	17.14
Lignite	12.866
Coke	23.367
Natural Gas (Btu/Cubic foot)	1,032
Liquid Fuels (Million Btu/Barrel)	
Motor gasoline	5.060
Aviation gasoline	5.048
Kerosene	5.670
Jet fuel, kerosene-type	5.670
Distillate fuel	5.825
Residual oil	6.287
Naphtha for petrochemicals	5.248
Petroleum coke	6.024
Other oil for petrochemicals	5.825
Special naphthas	5.248
Lubricants	6.065
Waxes	5.537
Asphalt	6.636
Still gas	6.000
Misc. products	5.796

Note: For petroleum and natural gas, *Monthly Energy Review February 2016* (EIA 2016). For coal ranks, *State Energy Data Report 1992* (EIA 1993). All values are given in higher heating values (gross calorific values).

6.6. Abbreviations

AAPFCO	American Association of Plant Food Control Officials
ABS	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene
AC	Air conditioner
ACC	American Chemistry Council
AEDT	FAA Aviation Environmental Design Tool
AEO	Annual Energy Outlook
AFEAS	Alternative Fluorocarbon Environmental Acceptability Study
AFV	Alternative fuel vehicle
AGA	American Gas Association
AHEF	Atmospheric and Health Effect Framework
AISI	American Iron and Steel Institute
ANGA	American Natural Gas Alliance
ANL	Argonne National Laboratory
APC	American Plastics Council
API	American Petroleum Institute
APTA	American Public Transportation Association
AR4	IPCC Fourth Assessment Report
AR5	IPCC Fifth Assessment Report
ARI	Advanced Resources International
ASAE	American Society of Agricultural Engineers
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BCEF	Biomass conversion and expansion factors
BEA	Bureau of Economic Analysis, U.S. Department of Commerce
BLM	Bureau of Land Management
BoC	Bureau of Census
BOD	Biological oxygen demand
BOD5	Biochemical oxygen demand over a 5-day period
BOEM	Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
BOEMRE	Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, Regulation and Enforcement
BOF	Basic oxygen furnace
BRS	Biennial Reporting System
BTS	Bureau of Transportation Statistics, U.S. Department of Transportation
Btu	British thermal unit
C	Carbon
C&EN	Chemical and Engineering News
CAAA	Clean Air Act Amendments of 1990
CAPP	Canadian Association of Petroleum Producers
CARB	California Air Resources Board
CBI	Confidential business information
C-CAP	Coastal Change Analysis Program
CDAP	Chemical Data Access Tool
CEFM	Cattle Enteric Fermentation Model
CEMS	Continuous emission monitoring system
CFC	Chlorofluorocarbon
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CGA	Compressed Gas Association
CH ₄	Methane
CHP	Combined heat and power
CIGRE	International Council on Large Electric Systems
CKD	Cement kiln dust
CLE	Crown Light Exposure
CMA	Chemical Manufacturer's Association
CMM	Coal mine methane
CMOP	Coalbed Methane Outreach Program
CMR	Chemical Market Reporter
CNG	Compressed natural gas
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
COGCC	Colorado Oil and Gas Conservation Commission

CRF	Common Reporting Format
CRM	Component ratio method
CRP	Conservation Reserve Program
CTIC	Conservation Technology Information Center
CVD	Chemical vapor deposition
CWNS	Clean Watershed Needs Survey
d.b.h	Diameter breast height
DE	Digestible energy
DESC	Defense Energy Support Center-DoD's defense logistics agency
DFAMS	Defense Fuels Automated Management System
DHS	Department of Homeland Security
DM	Dry matter
DOC	Degradable organic carbon
DOC	U.S. Department of Commerce
DoD	U.S. Department of Defense
DOE	U.S. Department of Energy
DOI	U.S. Department of the Interior
DOT	U.S. Department of Transportation
DRI	Direct Reduced Iron
EAF	Electric arc furnace
EDB	Aircraft Engine Emissions Databank
EDF	Environmental Defense Fund
EER	Energy economy ratio
EF	Emission factor
EFMA	European Fertilizer Manufacturers Association
EJ	Exajoule
EGR	Exhaust gas recirculation
EGU	Electric generating unit
EIA	Energy Information Administration, U.S. Department of Energy
EIIP	Emissions Inventory Improvement Program
EOR	Enhanced oil recovery
EPA	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
ERS	Economic Research Service
ETMS	Enhanced Traffic Management System
EV	Electric vehicle
EVI	Enhanced Vegetation Index
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organization
FAOSTAT	Food and Agricultural Organization database
FCCC	Framework Convention on Climate Change
FEB	Fiber Economics Bureau
FERC	Federal Energy Regulatory Commission
FGD	Flue gas desulfurization
FHWA	Federal Highway Administration
FIA	Forest Inventory and Analysis
FIADB	Forest Inventory and Analysis Database
FIPR	Florida Institute of Phosphate Research
FQSV	First-quarter of silicon volume
FSA	Farm Service Agency
FTP	Federal Test Procedure
g	Gram
GCV	Gross calorific value
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GHGRP	Greenhouse Gas Reporting Program
GJ	Gigajoule
GOADS	Gulf Offshore Activity Data System

GPG	Good Practice Guidance
GRI	Gas Research Institute
GSAM	Gas Systems Analysis Model
GTI	Gas Technology Institute
GWP	Global warming potential
ha	Hectare
HBFC	Hydrobromofluorocarbon
HC	Hydrocarbon
HCFC	Hydrochlorofluorocarbon
HDDV	Heavy duty diesel vehicle
HDGV	Heavy duty gas vehicle
HDPE	High density polyethylene
HFC	Hydrofluorocarbon
HFE	Hydrofluoroethers
HHV	Higher Heating Value
HMA	Hot Mix Asphalt
HMIWI	Hospital/medical/infectious waste incinerator
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HTS	Harmonized Tariff Schedule
HWP	Harvested wood product
IBF	International bunker fuels
IC	Integrated Circuit
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
ICE	Internal combustion engine
IDB	Integrated Database
IEA	International Energy Agency
IFO	Intermediate Fuel Oil
IISRP	International Institute of Synthetic Rubber Products
ILENR	Illinois Department of Energy and Natural Resources
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IPAA	Independent Petroleum Association of America
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPPU	Industrial Processes and Product Use
ITC	U.S. International Trade Commission
ITRS	International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors
JWR	Jim Walters Resources
KCA	Key category analysis
kg	Kilogram
kt	Kiloton
kWh	Kilowatt hour
LDDT	Light duty diesel truck
LDDV	Light duty diesel vehicle
LDGT	Light duty gas truck
LDGV	Light duty gas vehicle
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
LDT	Light-duty truck
LDV	Light-duty vehicle
LEV	Low emission vehicles
LFG	Landfill gas
LFGTE	Landfill gas-to-energy
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LKD	Lime kiln dust
LLDPE	Linear low density polyethylene
LMOP	EPA's Landfill Methane Outreach Program
LNG	Liquefied natural gas
LPG	Liquefied petroleum gas(es)
LTO	Landing and take-off
LULUCF	Land use, land-use change, and forestry
MARPOL	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MC	Motorcycle
MCF	Methane conversion factor
MCL	Maximum Contaminant Levels

MCFD	Thousand cubic feet per day
MDI	Metered dose inhalers
MECS	EIA Manufacturer's Energy Consumption Survey
MEM	Micro-electromechanical systems
MER	Monthly Energy Review
MGO	Marine gas oil
MJ	Megajoule
MLRA	Major Land Resource Area
mm	Millimeter
MMBtu	Million British thermal units
MMCF	Million cubic feet
MMCFD	Million cubic feet per day
MMS	Minerals Management Service
MMT	Million Metric Tons
MMTCE	Million metric tons carbon equivalent
MMT CO ₂ Eq.	Million metric tons carbon dioxide equivalent
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MOVES	U.S. EPA's Motor Vehicle Emission Simulator model
MPG	Miles per gallon
MRLC	Multi-Resolution Land Characteristics Consortium
MRV	Monitoring, reporting, and verification
MSHA	Mine Safety and Health Administration
MSW	Municipal solid waste
MT	Metric ton
MTBE	Methyl Tertiary Butyl Ether
MTBS	Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity
MVAC	Motor vehicle air conditioning
MY	Model year
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NA	Not available
NACWA	National Association of Clean Water Agencies
NAHMS	National Animal Health Monitoring System
NAICS	North American Industry Classification System
NAPAP	National Acid Precipitation and Assessment Program
NARR	North American Regional Reanalysis Product
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NASF	National Association of State Foresters
NASS	USDA's National Agriculture Statistics Service
NC	No change
NCASI	National Council of Air and Stream Improvement
NCV	Net calorific value
NE	Not estimated
NEI	National Emissions Inventory
NEMA	National Electrical Manufacturers Association
NEMS	National Energy Modeling System
NESHAP	National Emission Standards for Hazardous Air Pollutants
NEU	Non-Energy Use
NEV	Neighborhood Electric Vehicle
NF ₃	Nitrogen trifluoride
NGHGI	National Greenhouse Gas Inventory
NGL	Natural gas liquids
NIR	National Inventory Report
NLA	National Lime Association
NLCD	National Land Cover Dataset
NMOC	Non-methane organic compounds
NMVOC	Non-methane volatile organic compound

NO	Nitric oxide
NO	Not occurring
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NPRA	National Petroleum and Refiners Association
NRC	National Research Council
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service
NRI	National Resources Inventory
NSCEP	National Service Center for Environmental Publications
NSCR	Non-selective catalytic reduction
NSPS	New source performance standards
NWS	National Weather Service
OAG	Official Airline Guide
OAP	EPA Office of Atmospheric Programs
OAQPS	EPA Office of Air Quality Planning and Standards
ODP	Ozone depleting potential
ODS	Ozone depleting substances
OECD	Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development
OEM	Original equipment manufacturers
OGJ	Oil & Gas Journal
OH	Hydroxyl radical
OMS	EPA Office of Mobile Sources
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
OTA	Office of Technology Assessment
OTAQ	EPA Office of Transportation and Air Quality
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PCC	Precipitate calcium carbonate
PDF	Probability Density Function
PECVD	Plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PET	Potential evapotranspiration
PEVM	PFC Emissions Vintage Model
PFC	Perfluorocarbon
PFPE	Perfluoropolyether
PHMSA	Pipeline and Hazardous Materials Safety Administration
PI	Productivity index
POTW	Publicly Owned Treatment Works
ppbv	Parts per billion (10 ⁹) by volume
ppm	Parts per million
ppmv	Parts per million (10 ⁶) by volume
pptv	Parts per trillion (10 ¹²) by volume
PRP	Pasture/Range/Paddock
PS	Polystyrene
PSU	Primary Sample Unit
PU	Polyurethane
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
PV	Photovoltaic
QA/QC	Quality Assurance and Quality Control
QBtu	Quadrillion Btu
R&D	Research and Development
RECs	Reduced Emissions Completions
RCRA	Resource Conservation and Recovery Act
RMA	Rubber Manufacturers' Association
RPA	Resources Planning Act
RTO	Regression-through-the-origin
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SAGE	System for assessing Aviation's Global Emissions
SAN	Styrene Acrylonitrile
SAR	IPCC Second Assessment Report
SCR	Selective catalytic reduction

SCSE	South central and southeastern coastal
SEC	Securities and Exchange Commission
SEMI	Semiconductor Equipment and Materials Industry
SF ₆	Sulfur hexafluoride
SICAS	Semiconductor International Capacity Statistics
SNAP	Significant New Alternative Policy Program
SNG	Synthetic natural gas
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SOG	State of Garbage survey
SOHIO	Standard Oil Company of Ohio
SSURGO	Soil Survey Geographic Database
STMC	Scrap Tire Management Council
SULEV	Super Ultra Low Emissions Vehicle
SWANA	Solid Waste Association of North America
SWDS	Solid waste disposal sites
TA	Treated anaerobically (wastewater)
TAM	Typical animal mass
TAME	Tertiary amyl methyl ether
TAR	IPCC Third Assessment Report
TBtu	Trillion Btu
TDN	Total digestible nutrients
TEDB	Transportation Energy Data Book
TFI	The Fertilizer Institute
TIGER	Topologically Integrated Geographic Encoding and Referencing survey
TJ	Terajoule
TLEV	Traditional low emissions vehicle
TMLA	Total Manufactured Layer Area
TRI	Toxic Release Inventory
TSDF	Hazardous waste treatment, storage, and disposal facility
TVA	Tennessee Valley Authority
UAN	Urea ammonium nitrate
UDI	Utility Data Institute
UFORE	U.S. Forest Service's Urban Forest Effects model
UG	Underground (coal mining)
U.S.	United States
U.S. ITC	United States International Trade Commission
UEP	United Egg Producers
ULEV	Ultra low emission vehicle
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USAA	U.S. Aluminum Association
USAF	United States Air Force
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USFS	United States Forest Service
USGS	United States Geological Survey
VAIP	EPA's Voluntary Aluminum Industrial Partnership
VAM	Ventilation air methane
VKT	Vehicle kilometers traveled
VMT	Vehicle miles traveled
VOCs	Volatile organic compounds
VS	Volatile solids
WERF	Water Environment Research Federation
WFF	World Fab Forecast (previously WFW, World Fab Watch)
WGC	World Gas Conference
WIP	Waste in place
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

WMS	Waste management systems
WTE	Waste-to-energy
WW	Wastewater
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant
ZEVs	Zero emissions vehicles

6.7. Chemical Formulas

Table A-300: Guide to Chemical Formulas

Symbol	Name
Al	Aluminum
Al ₂ O ₃	Aluminum Oxide
Br	Bromine
C	Carbon
CH ₄	Methane
C ₂ H ₆	Ethane
C ₃ H ₈	Propane
CF ₄	Perfluoromethane
C ₂ F ₆	Perfluoroethane, hexafluoroethane
c-C ₃ F ₆	Perfluorocyclopropane
C ₃ F ₈	Perfluoropropane
c-C ₄ F ₈	Perfluorocyclobutane
C ₄ F ₁₀	Perfluorobutane
C ₅ F ₁₂	Perfluoropentane
C ₆ F ₁₄	Perfluorohexane
CF ₃ I	Trifluoroiodomethane
CFCl ₃	Trichlorofluoromethane (CFC-11)
CF ₂ Cl ₂	Dichlorodifluoromethane (CFC-12)
CF ₃ Cl	Chlorotrifluoromethane (CFC-13)
C ₂ F ₃ Cl ₃	Trichlorotrifluoroethane (CFC-113)*
CCl ₃ CF ₃	CFC-113a*
C ₂ F ₄ Cl ₂	Dichlorotetrafluoroethane (CFC-114)
C ₂ F ₅ Cl	Chloropentafluoroethane (CFC-115)
CHCl ₂ F	HCFC-21
CHF ₂ Cl	Chlorodifluoromethane (HCFC-22)
C ₂ F ₃ HCl ₂	HCFC-123
C ₂ F ₄ HCl	HCFC-124
C ₂ FH ₃ Cl ₂	HCFC-141b
C ₂ H ₃ F ₂ Cl	HCFC-142b
CF ₃ CF ₂ CHCl ₂	HCFC-225ca
CClF ₂ CF ₂ CHClF	HCFC-225cb
CCl ₄	Carbon tetrachloride
CHClCCl ₂	Trichloroethylene
CCl ₂ CCl ₂	Perchloroethylene, tetrachloroethene
CH ₃ Cl	Methylchloride
CH ₃ CCl ₃	Methylchloroform
CH ₂ Cl ₂	Methylenechloride
CHCl ₃	Chloroform, trichloromethane
CHF ₃	HFC-23
CH ₂ F ₂	HFC-32
CH ₃ F	HFC-41
C ₂ HF ₅	HFC-125
C ₂ H ₂ F ₄	HFC-134
CH ₂ FCF ₃	HFC-134a
C ₂ H ₃ F ₃	HFC-143*
C ₂ H ₃ F ₃	HFC-143a*
CH ₂ FCH ₂ F	HFC-152*
C ₂ H ₄ F ₂	HFC-152a*
CH ₃ CH ₂ F	HFC-161
C ₃ HF ₇	HFC-227ea
CF ₃ CF ₂ CH ₂ F	HFC-236cb
CF ₃ CHFCHF ₂	HFC-236ea

C ₃ H ₂ F ₆	HFC-236fa
C ₃ H ₃ F ₅	HFC-245ca
CHF ₂ CH ₂ CF ₃	HFC-245fa
CF ₃ CH ₂ CF ₂ CH ₃	HFC-365mfc
C ₆ H ₂ F ₁₀	HFC-43-10mee
CF ₃ OCHF ₂	HFE-125
CF ₂ HOCHF ₂ H	HFE-134
CH ₃ OCF ₃	HFE-143a
CF ₃ CHFOCF ₃	HFE-227ea
CF ₃ CHClOCHF ₂	HCFE-235da2
CF ₃ CHFOCHF ₂	HFE-236ea2
CF ₃ CH ₂ OCF ₃	HFE-236fa
CF ₃ CF ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-245cb2
CHF ₂ CH ₂ OCF ₃	HFE-245fa1
CF ₃ CH ₂ OCHF ₂	HFE-245fa2
CHF ₂ CF ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-254cb2
CF ₃ CH ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-263fb2
CF ₃ CF ₂ OCF ₂ CHF ₂	HFE-329mcc2
CF ₃ CF ₂ OCH ₂ CF ₃	HFE-338mcf2
CF ₃ CF ₂ CF ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-347mcc3
CF ₃ CF ₂ OCH ₂ CHF ₂	HFE-347mcf2
CF ₃ CHFCF ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-356mec3
CHF ₂ CF ₂ CF ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-356pcc3
CHF ₂ CF ₂ OCH ₂ CHF ₂	HFE-356pcf2
CHF ₂ CF ₂ CH ₂ OCHF ₂	HFE-356pcf3
CF ₃ CF ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₃	HFE-365mcf3
CHF ₂ CF ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₃	HFE-374pcf2
C ₄ F ₉ OCH ₃	HFE-7100
C ₄ F ₉ OC ₂ H ₅	HFE-7200
CHF ₂ OCF ₂ OC ₂ F ₄ OCHF ₂	H-Galden 1040x
CHF ₂ OCF ₂ OCHF ₂	HG-10
CHF ₂ OCF ₂ CF ₂ OCHF ₂	HG-01
CH ₃ OCH ₃	Dimethyl ether
CH ₂ Br ₂	Dibromomethane
CH ₂ BrCl	Dibromochloromethane
CHBr ₃	Tribromomethane
CHBrF ₂	Bromodifluoromethane
CH ₃ Br	Methylbromide
CF ₂ BrCl	Bromodichloromethane (Halon 1211)
CF ₃ Br(CBrF ₃)	Bromotrifluoromethane (Halon 1301)
CF ₃ I	FIC-1311
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CaCO ₃	Calcium carbonate, Limestone
CaMg(CO ₃) ₂	Dolomite
CaO	Calcium oxide, Lime
Cl	atomic Chlorine
F	Fluorine
Fe	Iron
Fe ₂ O ₃	Ferric oxide
FeSi	Ferrosilicon
H, H ₂	atomic Hydrogen, molecular Hydrogen
H ₂ O	Water
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen peroxide
OH	Hydroxyl
N, N ₂	atomic Nitrogen, molecular Nitrogen
NH ₃	Ammonia
NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium ion
HNO ₃	Nitric acid
MgO	Magnesium oxide
NF ₃	Nitrogen trifluoride
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide

NO	Nitric oxide
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
NO ₃	Nitrate radical
Na	Sodium
Na ₂ CO ₃	Sodium carbonate, soda ash
Na ₃ AlF ₆	Synthetic cryolite
O, O ₂	atomic Oxygen, molecular Oxygen
O ₃	Ozone
S	atomic Sulfur
H ₂ SO ₄	Sulfuric acid
SF ₆	Sulfur hexafluoride
SF ₅ CF ₃	Trifluoromethylsulphur pentafluoride
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
Si	Silicon
SiC	Silicon carbide
SiO ₂	Quartz

* Distinct isomers.

References

- EIA (2016) *Monthly Energy Review, February 2016*. Energy Information Administration, U.S. Department of Energy, Washington, DC. DOE/EIA-0035(2016/02). February 2016.
- EIA (2007) *Emissions of Greenhouse Gases in the United States 2006, Draft Report*. Office of Integrated Analysis and Forecasting, Energy Information Administration, U.S. Department of Energy, Washington, DC. DOE-EIA-0573(2006).
- EIA (1998) *Emissions of Greenhouse Gases in the United States*, DOE/EIA-0573(97), Energy Information Administration, U.S. Department of Energy. Washington, DC. October.
- EIA (1993) *State Energy Data Report 1992*, DOE/EIA-0214(93), Energy Information Administration, U.S. Department of Energy. Washington, DC. December.
- EPA (2015) "1970 - 2014 Average annual emissions, all criteria pollutants in MS Excel." National Emissions Inventory (NEI) Air Pollutant Emissions Trends Data. Office of Air Quality Planning and Standards, March 2015. Available online at <<http://www.epa.gov/ttn/chief/trends/index.html>>.
- EPA (2003) E-mail correspondence. Air pollutant data. Office of Air Pollution to the Office of Air Quality Planning and Standards, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). December 22, 2003.
- IPCC (2013) *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp.
- IPCC (2007) *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. S. Solomon, D. Qin, M. Manning, Z. Chen, M. Marquis, K.B. Averyt, M. Tignor and H.L. Miller (eds.). Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, United Kingdom 996 pp.
- IPCC (2001) *Climate Change 2001: The Scientific Basis. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, J.T. Houghton, Y. Ding, D.J. Griggs, M. Noguer, P.J. van der Linden, X. Dai, C.A. Johnson, and K. Maskell (eds.). Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, United Kingdom.
- IPCC (1996) *Climate Change 1995: The Science of Climate Change. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, J.T. Houghton, L.G. Meira Filho, B.A. Callander, N. Harris, A. Kattenberg, and K. Maskell. (eds.). Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, United Kingdom.